

ASSESSMENT OF MORPHOMETRIC TRAITS AS PREDICTORS OF BODY WEIGHT IN FULANI ECOTYPE, FUNAAB ALPHA CHICKENS AND THEIR RECIPROCAL CROSSES USING CORRELATION ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the growth performance and phenotypic correlations among morphometric traits of the Fulani ecotype, FUNAAB Alpha chicken, and their reciprocal crosses under uniform management conditions. A total of sixty (60) parent birds were used to generate one hundred and twenty (120) F1 progeny across four genetic groups in a completely randomized design. Data was collected on body weight and linear body measurements, including beak length, head length, neck length, wing length, wing span, shank length, drumstick length and body girth. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Pearson correlation analysis were conducted using SPSS, and treatment means were separated using Duncan's Multiple Range Test. Results revealed significant ($p < 0.05$) differences among treatments for all evaluated traits. The FUNAAB Male \times FUNAAB alpha male (T1) consistently recorded superior values for body weight (462.01g) and most morphometric parameters compared to other groups, while the Fulani ecotype purebred (T2) showed the lowest performance. Positive and significant phenotypic correlations were observed between body weight and most morphometric traits across treatments, particularly wing length, wingspan, shank length, and body girth. The findings highlight the potential of morphometric traits as indirect selection criteria and confirm the effectiveness of crossbreeding in improving growth performance in indigenous chickens. These results provide valuable insights for designing sustainable genetic improvement programs.

Keywords: Indigenous chickens, morphometric traits, body weight prediction, correlation analysis, crossbreeding, genetic improvement

INTRODUCTION

Poultry production plays a crucial role in animal protein supply and improving livelihoods in Nigeria, as it remains one of the fastest-growing livestock sectors globally, contributing significantly to food security, income generation, and nutritional sustainability. Poultry contributes

significantly to national livestock output and serves as a major source of affordable animal protein (Ojedapo *et al.*, 2010). Indigenous chickens constitute over 60% of the total chicken population in Nigeria (Fayeye, 2011), highlighting their importance in rural production systems. The indigenous chickens play a dominant

role due to their adaptability to harsh environmental conditions, resistance to endemic diseases, and ability to thrive under low-input management systems (Gueye, 2002; Aboe *et al.*, 2006). Their role in food security, income generation, and socio-cultural functions among rural households is well documented (Abdelqader *et al.*, 2007). Despite these advantages, indigenous chickens are generally characterized by poor growth rates, low body weight, and reduced productivity compared to improved or exotic breeds.

Understanding the relationships among growth-related traits is fundamental for designing effective breeding programs. Body weight is a primary economic trait in poultry production, directly influencing market value and profitability. However, direct measurement of body weight may not always be feasible in rural or resource-limited settings. Consequently, morphometric traits—quantitative measurements of body structure—have gained importance as alternative indicators of growth performance. The development of improved indigenous strains such as the FUNAAB Alpha chicken represents a deliberate effort toward combining adaptability with improved growth and egg production (Adebambo, 2015). However, limited information exists on the growth performance and morphometric characteristics of these improved breeds and their crosses with local ecotypes.

Growth in poultry is a dynamic biological process influenced by genetic and environmental factors. Body weight is a key economic trait as it directly affects market value and profitability (Momoh and Kershima, 2008). Morphometric traits, quantitative measurements of body structure, have been shown to correlate with

body weight and can serve as indirect selection criteria, particularly in rural settings where weighing scales may not be readily available (Semacula *et al.*, 2011). Traits such as shank length, body girth, and wing length are considered indicators of skeletal and muscular development (Julius, 2020). Moreover, phenotypic correlations between body weight and linear body measurements provide valuable information for designing breeding programs and constructing effective selection indices (Chineke *et al.*, 2002).

Several studies have demonstrated significant correlations between body weight and linear body measurements such as wing length, shank length, and body girth. These relationships suggest that morphometric traits can be used as indirect selection criteria for improving growth performance. Previous studies have demonstrated positive relationships between body weight and linear body traits in chickens (Jubril *et al.*, 2023; Yakubu and Salako, 2009). Such relationships suggest that improvement in certain morphometric parameters may lead to corresponding increases in body weight. However, information on the phenotypic correlations among morphometric traits of the Fulani ecotype, FUNAAB Alpha chickens, and their reciprocal crosses remain scarce.

Despite the growing interest in morphometric characterization, limited information exists on the integration of these traits in the Fulani ecotype and FUNAAB Alpha chickens and their reciprocal crosses. This study was therefore designed to evaluate the phenotypic relationships between body weight and morphometric traits in the Fulani ecotype, FUNAAB Alpha chickens, and their reciprocal crosses.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Site

The experiment was conducted at the Teaching and Research Farm of the University of Abuja, Nigeria, located within the Guinea Savannah agro-ecological zone. A tropical climate with distinct wet and dry seasons characterizes the area.

Experimental Birds and Breeding Design

A total of 60 parental birds comprising Fulani ecotype and FUNAAB Alpha chickens were used to generate a total of 120 chicks in this study. The parental birds were randomly assigned to four mating groups to produce F1 progeny:

Treatment one: FAM x FAF (3 FUNAAB males and 12 FUNAAB females).

Treatment two: FEM × FEF (3 Fulani ecotype male and 12 Fulani ecotype female chicken).

Treatment three: FAM x FEF (3 FUNAAB males and 12 Fulani ecotype females).

Treatment four: FEM x FAF (3 Fulani ecotype males and 12 FUNAAB females).

Each mating group consisted of one male and four female birds, housed independently. Eggs were collected, incubated, and hatched separately for each group.

Management of Experimental Birds

Chicks were brooded for four weeks and subsequently reared for eight weeks under uniform management conditions. Birds were fed a commercial diet containing approximately 18% crude protein and 2750 kcal/kg metabolizable energy. Clean water was provided ad libitum, and routine vaccination and health management practices were followed.

Experimental design:

The experiment was conducted using a completely randomized design (CRD).

Data Collection

The data collected are body weight and body linear measurements.

Parameters Collected

The parameters collected include neck length, beak length, shank length, thigh length, Breast width, body weight, wing length and body length. Trait description and measurement followed the guidelines of FAO (2012). The traits measured (in cm) are:

- i. Body weight (BW) was measured using an electronic digital scale.
- ii. Beak length (BKL) was from the tip of the upper beak to either the rostral angle of the nostril or to the skull insertion point.
- iii. Neck length was measured by gently straightening out the neck, and the length was measured with a tape rule as neck length (NEL).
- iv. Head length: was measured from the occipital bone to the tip of the beak with the aid of a Venier caliper
- v. Wing length (WNL) was measured from the shoulder joint to the extremity of the terminal phalanx.
- vi. Wing Span (WNS): was measured with wings fully stretched, measuring from the tip of the longest primary feather on one wing to the tip of the longest primary feather on the other wing
- vii. The tarso-metatarsus (shank length) (SHL) was obtained by measuring from the hock joint to the base of the three toes
- viii. Drum stick (DM) was taken from the hock joint to the hinge joint.
- ix. Body girth (BGT) was measured across the keel bones from the left armpit to the right armpit.

To ensure accuracy, each measurement was

taken twice. All the measurements were taken by the same person using tape rule calibrated in centimeters (cm). These traits were measured every week up to the end of the experiment.

Statistical Analysis

Data were subjected to Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) using the General Linear Model procedure of SPSS (version 20). Significant treatment means were separated using Duncan's Multiple Range Test. Phenotypic correlations among growth and morphometric traits were determined using Pearson's correlation coefficients

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Morphometric Indices and Performance of Fulani Ecotype, FUNAAB Alpha and Their Reciprocal Crosses

Table 1 showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were observed among the genetic

groups for body weight. The FUNAAB Alpha purebred group (T1) recorded the highest body weight, followed by the crossbred groups (T3 and T4), while the Fulani ecotype (T2) recorded the lowest values. Although FUNAAB Alpha (T1) showed higher values for several traits, some parameters such as shank length were higher in crossbred groups (T3), indicating trait-specific variation, while the improved performance of crossbreds suggests the presence of heterosis.

All morphometric traits showed significant variation across treatments. FUNAAB Alpha birds consistently exhibited higher values for most traits, including wing length, wing span, and body girth. Crossbred groups showed intermediate values, while the Fulani ecotype recorded the lowest measurements.

Table 1. Morphometric Indices and Performance of Fulani Ecotype, FUNAAB Alpha and Their Reciprocal Crosses

Parameters	T1	T2	T3	T4	SEM
Body weight (g)	462.01 ^a	307.09 ^c	387.00 ^b	399.02 ^{ab}	20.01
Beak length (cm)	2.05 ^a	1.29 ^b	1.79 ^a	1.82 ^a	0.06
Neck length (cm)	5.92 ^a	2.20 ^d	3.77 ^c	4.68 ^b	0.17
Head length (cm)	4.78 ^a	2.77 ^c	3.67 ^b	4.35 ^a	0.49
Wing length (cm)	19.13 ^a	4.74 ^d	11.96 ^c	14.56 ^b	1.00
Wing span (cm)	39.06 ^a	10.08 ^d	26.67 ^c	31.33 ^b	0.11
Shank length (cm)	5.28 ^{ab}	2.77 ^c	6.42 ^a	4.13 ^b	0.24
Drumstick (cm)	6.98 ^a	3.67 ^b	5.40 ^{ab}	5.30 ^{ab}	0.32
Body girth (cm)	19.13 ^a	9.42 ^c	12.97 ^b	15.98 ^b	0.28

^{abcd} Means in the same row with different superscripts differ significantly ($P < 0.05$)

(g) = gram, SEM = Standard error of mean

Correlated Phenotypic Relationships Among Morphometric Traits (cm) of Fulani Ecotype, FUNAAB Alpha and Their Reciprocal Crosses at 8 Weeks of Age

Table 2 shows the correlated relationship between morphometric traits of Fulani ecotype, FUNAAB alpha and their reciprocal crosses at 8 weeks of age. The result shows a positive and significant

correlation among traits evaluated in T₁, T₂ and T₄, with the highest correlation between WNS and WNL in T₂ (r = 0.97^{**}: P < 0.05) and between SHL and WNL in T₄ (r = 0.96^{xx}: P < 0.05), showing that each trait influences another. However, negative and no significant correlation between SHL, BW and BKL was found in T₃ (-0.10, -0.04: P < 0.05), respectively.

Table 2. Correlated Phenotypic Relationships Among Morphometric Traits (cm) of Fulani Ecotype, FUNAAB Alpha and Their Reciprocal Crosses at 8 Weeks of Age

	Traits	BW	BKL	NKL	HL	WNL	WNS	SHL	DM	BGT
T1	BW	1								
	BKL	0.85 ^{**}	1							
	NKL	0.74 ^{**}	0.81 ^{**}	1						
	HL	0.77 ^{**}	0.64 ^{**}	0.94 ^{**}	1					
	WNL	0.63 ^{**}	0.66 ^{**}	0.70 ^{**}	0.69 ^{**}	1				
	WNS	0.80 ^{**}	0.88 ^{**}	0.84 ^{**}	0.84 ^{**}	0.79 ^{**}	1			
	SHL	0.74 ^{**}	0.80 ^{**}	0.79 ^{**}	0.83 ^{**}	0.58 ^{**}	0.70 ^{**}	1		
	DM	0.54 ^{**}	0.61 ^{**}	0.49 ^{**}	0.51 ^{**}	0.06 ^{**}	0.49 ^{**}	0.48 ^{**}	1	
	BGT	0.79 ^{**}	0.88 ^{**}	0.92 ^{**}	0.89 ^{**}	0.74 ^{**}	0.83 ^{**}	0.79 ^{**}	0.61 ^{**}	1
T2	BW	1								
	BKL	0.38 ^{**}	1							
	NKL	0.12	0.30 [*]	1						
	HL	0.29 [*]	0.83 ^{**}	0.33 ^{**}	1					
	WNL	0.26 [*]	0.72 ^{**}	0.40 ^{**}	0.79 ^{**}	1				
	WNS	0.22	0.61 ^{**}	0.38 ^{**}	0.75 ^{**}	0.97 ^{**}	1			
	SHL	0.34 ^{**}	0.95 ^{**}	0.58 ^{**}	0.87 ^{**}	0.81 ^{**}	0.72 ^{**}	1		
	DM	0.10	0.26 [*]	0.95 ^{**}	0.28 [*]	0.29 [*]	0.27 [*]	0.33 ^{**}	1	
	BGT	0.10	0.42 ^{**}	0.16	0.34 ^{**}	0.35 ^{**}	0.31 [*]	0.43 ^{**}	0.12 [*]	1
T3	BW	1								
	BKL	0.47 ^{**}	1							
	NKL	0.78 ^{**}	0.58 ^{**}	1						
	HL	0.71 ^{**}	0.59 ^{**}	0.94 ^{**}	1					
	WNL	0.67 ^{**}	0.57 ^{**}	0.90 ^{**}	0.95 ^{**}	1				
	WNS	0.71 ^{**}	0.59 ^{**}	0.91 ^{**}	0.95 ^{**}	0.98 ^{**}	1			

	BW	1								
	BKL	0.86**	1							
	NKL	0.74**	0.90**	1						
	HL	0.74**	0.89**	0.93**	1					
T4	WNL	0.75**	0.91**	0.87**	0.92**	1				
	WNS	0.76**	0.91**	0.84**	0.89**	0.97**	1			
	SHL	0.82**	0.93**	0.91**	0.94**	0.96**	0.94**	1		
	DM	0.66**	0.87**	0.83**	0.90**	0.93**	0.92**	0.91**	1	
	BGT	0.81**	0.92**	0.87**	0.91**	0.95**	0.93**	0.94**	0.86**	1

BW = Body weight, BKL = Beak length, NKL = Neck length, HL = Head length, SHL = Shank length, DM = Drumstick, BGT = Body girth, WNL = Wing length, WNS = Wing span, ** = highly significant (P<0.05), g = gram, cm = centimeters.

Correlation Among Morphometric Traits of Fulani Ecotype, FUNAAB Alpha and Their Reciprocal Crosses at 8 Weeks of Age

The correlation analysis revealed varying magnitudes of association between body weight and morphometric traits. Body weight showed moderate to strong positive correlations in T3 (r = 0.54**) and T4 (r = 0.62**), while T2 exhibited a weak negative correlation (r = -0.04). The strongest inter-treatment relationship was between T3 and T4 (r = 0.70**), suggesting similarity in growth expression among reciprocal crosses.

For individual traits, beak length showed moderate positive correlations in T1 and T2

(r = 0.54**), whereas wing length displayed contrasting trends, positive in T3 (r = 0.52**) but strongly negative in T2 (r = -0.86). Shank length exhibited positive relationships in T2 (r = 0.43**) and T4 (r = 0.60), reinforcing its importance as an indicator of skeletal growth.

Pearson's correlation analysis revealed strong positive relationships between body weight and several morphometric traits. Wing span, body girth, and shank length showed the highest correlations with body weight. These findings indicate that these traits are closely associated with growth performance and can serve as reliable indicators of body weight.

Table 3. Correlation Among Morphometric Traits of Fulani Ecotype, FUNAAB Alpha and Their Reciprocal Crosses at 8 Weeks of Age

Traits	Treatments	T1	T2	T3	T4
	T1				
Body weight	T2	-0.04			
	T3	0.54**	0.40**		
	T4	0.62**	0.28*	0.70**	1

Beak length	T1				
	T2	0.54**			
	T3	0.32**	0.21		
	T4	0.39**	-0.20	0.12	1
Neck length	T1				
	T2	0.70			
	T3	0.70**	-0.15		
	T4	0.43**	-0.01	0.10	1
Head length	T1				
	T2	0.31*			
	T3	0.59**	0.26		
	T4	0.22	-0.17	-0.05	1
Wing length	T1				
	T2	0.12			
	T3	0.52**	-0.86		
	T4	0.20	-0.10	-0.05	1
Wing span	T1				
	T2	-0.40			
	T3	0.44**	-0.19		
	T4	0.26	-0.20	-0.07	1
Shank length	T1				
	T2	0.43**			
	T3	-0.07	-0.08		
	T4	0.18	0.60	-0.03	1
Drumstick	T1				
	T2	0.02			
	T3	0.48**	-0.04		
	T4	0.15	0.04	0.06	1
Body girth	T1				
	T2	0.13			
	T3	0.20	0.04		
	T4	0.15	0.22	0.16	1

Discussion

Morphometric traits are indices used to predict live weight gain, examine relationship among economic characteristics, reproduction performance and to study the relationship between heredity and environment and such studies had found appreciation in selection and breeding (Jubril *et al.*, 2022; Owojori *et al.*, 2007). Body weight and conformation traits are the two important traits for measuring growth in the domestic chicken (Udeh and Ogbu, 2011).

The results of this finding are in agreement with the results of Okon and Ogundu (2006), who obtained high and positive phenotypic correlations between body weight and other body parameters namely: thigh length, chest circumference, breast width, keel length and shank length. They suggested that these parameters may be good indicators of body weight. Similarly, Okpeku *et al.* (2003) reported that body weight was positively correlated with body length, chest circumference, femur and crust but obtained negative and low correlation between body weight and tarsometatarsus (shank length) in chickens. They observed that the correlation coefficient at 3 weeks were generally weak and non-significant with some traits showing negative relationships. From these findings, wing span was the highest estimator of body weight at 8 weeks. Shank length was also positively correlated with body weight at 3, 6, 9, and 12 weeks. At 6 and 9 weeks, body weight was reported to be positively correlated with body girth, body length, keel length, shank length and width, which is also in line with the present studies.

These results suggest that body weight in broiler chicken can be rapidly predicted from these live body measurements at 8

weeks of age. This is in agreement with the findings of Jubril *et al.*, (2021), that body measurements can be effectively used to predict subsequent live weight. Okon and Ogundu (2006) observed that shank length had significant and positive correlation with thigh length, thigh circumference, breast width and keel length. Whereas, low but significant correlation was observed between shank length and body weight in turkey breeds of south eastern Nigeria. They also reported that thigh length had high and significant correlations with body weight, thigh circumference, breast width, keel length and shank length. They also obtained 26 highly significant correlations between chest circumferences (breast width) with body weight, thigh length and thigh circumference.

However, the negative correlations observed in this finding were in line with the research of Udeh and Ogbu (2011) who reported coefficient of correlations of body weight and body measurements of three strains of broiler chicken as ranged -0.05 to 0.76, -0.02 to 0.56 and -0.28 to 0.60 in Arbor Acre, Marshall and Ross strains respectively. They also reported that relationships between body weight and most of the body measurements were positive and no significant ($p > 0.05$) in the three strains of broilers. However, significant ($p < 0.01$) and positive correlations were recorded for shank length and breast width (0.62), thigh length and breast width (0.66), thigh length and wing length (0.64) and breast width and wing length (0.76) in Arbor Acre broiler.

The comparative morphometric traits evaluation of Fulani ecotype, FUNAAB alpha and their reciprocal crosses at 8 weeks of age presented in table 1. The means values of all the traits obtained in this

present study were lower than the values Akanno *et al.* (2007) for broiler birds this variation could be attributed to the differences in management practices, breeds, diet composition or environmental conditions.

The Correlation among morphometric traits of Fulani ecotype, FUNAAB alpha and their reciprocal crosses at 8 weeks of age presented in table 3. The results obtained in this study indicated negative and no significant ($P > 0.05$) correlation. Contrarily to this result findings, Yahaya *et al.* (2012) reported correlations coefficients of 0.916, 0.894, 0.861, 0.897, 0.977 and 0.963 obtained between body weight and neck length, shank length, thigh length, keel length, breast width and back length for Hubbard strain, while for Arbor acre strain the correlation values of 0.967, 0.974, 0.882, 0.935, 0.981 and 0.969, respectively was obtained between body weight and neck length, shank length, thigh length, keel length breast width and back length all indicating a strong positive relationship.

The superior growth performance of FUNAAB Alpha chickens observed in this study confirms the success of genetic improvement programs aimed at enhancing productivity. The intermediate performance

of crossbred groups suggests that crossbreeding is an effective strategy for improving growth traits in indigenous chickens. The strong positive correlations between body weight and morphometric traits observed in this study are consistent with previous findings. These relationships highlight the potential of using linear body measurements as indirect selection criteria in breeding programs.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated significant genetic variation in growth performance and morphometric traits among the Fulani ecotype, FUNAAB Alpha chickens, and their reciprocal crosses. Morphometric traits showed strong predictive relationships with body weight and can be effectively used as indirect selection criteria.

Crossbreeding significantly improved growth performance, highlighting its importance in sustainable poultry production. The integration of the correlation analysis technique provides a robust framework for understanding trait relationships and enhancing breeding programs.

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